

BEPSII-TS: A Global Historical Dataset of Temperature and Salinity in Sea-Ice Cores

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Introduction

Several sea-ice core data collation efforts within the sea-ice biogeochemistry (BGC) community have focused on biogeochemical parameters, most notably led under the auspices of the international BEPSII group (Biogeochemical Exchange Processes at the Sea Ice Interfaces, <https://sites.google.com/site/bepsiiwg140/home>). No equivalent effort has systematically compiled ice core temperature and salinity data, despite their physical importance. As these variables are routinely measured, such a collation is both feasible and valuable. This document describes the BEPSII-TS historical sea-ice core dataset, as depicted in **Figure 1**.

1. Data collation and pre-processing

Sea-ice salinity and temperature data from ice cores are measured following similar procedures across different research groups (Eicken et al., 2010; Tison et al., 2008). Sea-ice cores are extracted using either a manual or motorized corer. Immediately after extraction, core length is recorded, and *in situ* temperature is generally measured at approximately 5–10 cm intervals by inserting a temperature probe into freshly drilled holes 3–5 cm deep. The cores are then sectioned, stored, and transported to the laboratory for melting and processing, including salinity measurements for each section. In most cases, snow depth is measured near the time of coring, often multiple times, and then averaged.

Figure 1. Time series of normalised vertical profiles of sea-ice salinity (top two rows) and temperature (bottom two rows) for each month of the year, in the version 1.1 of the BEPSII-TS dataset. Month number is indicated in the upper right corner. Profiles from the Southern Hemisphere (SH) are shifted by six months, for best alignment with the Northern Hemisphere (NH).

Known measurement biases include a high temperature bias due to solar radiation warming under summer clear skies (Zhou et al., 2013), a low temperature bias in winter under cold air (Eicken et al., 2010), and a low salinity bias, especially at the base of the cores because of the loss of brine upon coring (Notz et al., 2005).

Each record was vertically arranged as shown in **Figure 2**, and data were stored in Excel files, following ASPeCt log-sheet standards (Meiners et al., 2012). Individual temperature measurements correspond to a unique mid-point core section depth, whereas salinity is an integrated measurement over core sections, for which upper and lower boundaries are given. Temperature and salinity data are generally independent and not available on the same vertical grid, so vertical interpolation is required to obtain both variables at consistent depths. Routines for this are available in the BEPSII Sea Ice Core Analyzer package (<https://sites.google.com/site/bepsiiwg140/science/data>).

Figure 2. Vertical arrangement of ice salinity data for a given ice core. z refers to the depths of core section edges, z_m is the mid-point depth, dz is section depth, S is salinity, T is temperature, cl is core length. Note that temperature is set the same way as salinity.

Our primary data sources were previous compilation efforts focusing on biogeochemical parameters (Fripiat et al., 2017; Lannuzel et al., 2016; Meiners et al., 2012, 2018). Additional core series were obtained from individual publications, logbooks, or directly from authors. Records were retained if valid temperature or salinity measurements were available. In total, 3,780 individual log sheets from 38 (37) cruises / voyages in the Northern (Southern) hemisphere were retained. These log sheets were then imported into MATLAB and stored as data arrays. **Table S1** lists these arrays, whereas **Tables S2** and **S3** list individual cruise / voyage data sources and characteristics.

Further processing steps were also applied. Salinity values were converted from practical to absolute salinities, using the TEOS-10 package (McDougall & Barker, 2011). A small number of salinity values exceeding 40 g/kg, originating from early Antarctic cruises, as well as temperature values above the local freezing point, were treated as missing (NaN). Section-length-weighted vertical averages of temperature and salinity were then calculated for each record.

Flags indicating valid data (`i_keep_S` and `i_keep_T`) are provided to identify values suitable for subsequent scientific analysis. As multiple sources contained duplicate cores, entries corresponding to the same core (i.e., identical latitude, longitude, sampling time, and mean salinity or temperature) were automatically identified and removed. Finally, metadata were standardized across cruises, including cruise name, reference, region, and drift and age classifications.

2. Basic statistics

		S-cores (%: with snow)	T-cores (%: with snow)	S&T-cores (%: with snow)
N _{cores}	Total	1474 (64.4%)	768 (72.2%)	709 (72.4%)
	Arctic	639 (64.6%)	516 (70.1%)	474 (71.1%)
	Antarctic	835 (64.3%)	252 (76.6%)	235 (74.9%)
N _{sections}	Total	18339	12206	11543
	Arctic	9832	9159	8588
	Antarctic	8507	3047	2955

Table 1. Database summary statistics. Number of unique cores and associated core sections in the whole database, split by hemisphere, for three classes of samples: S-cores (including a salinity measurement), T-cores (including a temperature measurement), and S&T-cores (including both a salinity measurement and a companion temperature measurement). Percentages indicate the proportion of cores with an ancillary snow-depth record.

Dataset Overview. In total, we compiled 1,474 unique cores with salinity measurements, 768 with temperature measurements, and 709 with both variables recorded (**Table 1**). Over 64% of the cores include ancillary snow depth records. Some cores contain missing sections; on average, the sampled vertical fraction of total core length is 93%.

In the Arctic, two thirds of the cores are from pack ice, and the other third from fast ice, while pack ice dominates (~85%) in the Antarctic. The distinction between first-year and multi-year ice is often unclear due to missing or inconsistently defined metadata. However, literature describing each campaign (**Tables S2 and S3**) indicates a significant proportion of multi-year ice in the dataset.

Sampling in space and time. By essence, sampling is uneven, introducing biases similar to those seen in previous collections (e.g., Meiners et al., 2012). Sampling biases are consistent across salinity (S), temperature (T), and combined S&T cores.

The regional distribution of data records is shown in **Figure 3**. Arctic cores are concentrated in the central Arctic, Fram Strait, Svalbard, and the Canadian Arctic, but no data are available from the Siberian shelf and Bering Seas. Antarctic cores align with existing compilations, with higher density in the Weddell, West Ross, and Pacific Sectors, and large data gaps in the Indian and East Ross Sectors.

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of observations. Colored symbols refer to S-cores, and black pluses are T-cores. Background colours show the average months of sea-ice coverage (OSI-450, 1979–2020).

Sampling is largely uneven seasonally (**Figure 4a**), reflecting fieldwork constraints. Core availability peaks in spring and early summer (March–June in the Arctic; September–December in the Antarctic), when field conditions are the easiest and supply ships are operating. Core availability is lowest in late summer–early fall (September–October in the Arctic; February–March in the Antarctic). Winter cores tend also to be less abundant. T-cores are particularly sparse, with March and April not represented in the Antarctic dataset. As **Figure 4b** indicates, the dataset spans slightly over two decades in the Arctic (1997–2021), if we exclude a few cores from the 1970s; and nearly four decades in the Antarctic (1981–2017).

Core length, section length and snow depth.

The core length distribution (**Figure 4c**), is bimodal in the Arctic and single-moded in the Antarctic. The average Arctic core length is 1.35 ± 0.66 m, compared to 1.04 ± 0.72 m in the Antarctic. Cores longer than 3 m represent less than 2% of the total, suggesting a focus on level ice and avoidance of thick, deformed ice during sampling.

The snow depth distribution (**Figure 4d**) approximates a log-normal pattern, though discontinuities suggest undersampling. Mean snow depth is 0.14 ± 0.19 m, with no significant inter-hemispheric difference despite distinct distributions. Antarctic cores slightly more frequently exceed 0.3 m of snow ($P=0.13$) compared to Arctic cores ($P=0.11$) but show a deficit between 0.15 and 0.2 m. Arctic snow depths above 0.5 m ($N=19$) are mostly limited to Greenland landfast ice sites, while extreme snow depths ($N=23$) are more geographically distributed in the Antarctic.

Section lengths (**Figure 4e**) are predominantly 5 cm or 10 cm, consistent with common practice in the sea-ice research community.

Figure 4. Sampling statistics: Probability histograms of (a) sampling month, (b) sampling year, (c) core length, (d) snow depth, (e) core section length. For panels a-d, probabilities are split for S-cores, T-cores and S&T-cores. Sampling probability increases upwards (downwards) for NH (SH) cores.

3. Outlook

The BEPSII-TS dataset compiles temperature and salinity profiles from a wide range of sources, processed using consistent quality control and harmonization procedures. Careful quality control and removal of duplicate cores, resulting in the largest coherent dataset of this kind, provides a unique resource on sea-ice temperature and salinity from both poles. The dataset seems reasonably well-suited for examining hemispheric differences, seasonal variations, and vertical salinity profiles within sea ice. However, the dataset has known systematic errors, heterogeneous sampling, including large sampling gaps for some months (particularly in fall) and specific regions. Future updates will attempt to address these gaps.

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Table S1. Key variables included in the database and their description. An ice core has a maximum of 61 sections (giving 62 section edges).

Name	Size	Definition	Units
Nr		Total number of records	
Date	[Nr]	Date	YYYYMMDD
Lon	[Nr]	Longitude	[-180°,180°]
Lat	[Nr]	Latitude	[-90°,90°]
CoreID	[Nr]	Core identification string	string
Cruise	[Nr]	Cruise name	string
type	[Nr]	Drift class (encountered in the cruise)	'pack' or 'fast'
age	[Nr]	Age class (encountered during the cruise)	FY, 'MY', 'FY/MY'
hi	[Nr]	Ice thickness (from meta-data)	[m]
hs	[Nr]	Snow depth (from meta-data)	[m]
T	[Nr,61]	Ice Temperature	[°C]
z_T	[Nr,62]	Section edge depth, temperature measurement	[m]
zm_T	[Nr,61]	Mid-point section depth, temperature measurement	[m]
dz_T	[Nr,61]	Section thickness, temperature measurement	[m]
cl_T	[Nr]	Length of temperature core	[m]
tsl_T	[Nr]	Total section length, temperature core	[m]
Nd_T	[Nr]	Number of core sections with valid temperature record	
Nb_T	[Nr]	Number of T-core sections in log-sheet (incl. empty cells)	
S	[Nr,61]	Ice Salinity	[g/kg]
z_S	[Nr,62]	Section edge depth, salinity measurement	[m]
zm_S	[Nr,61]	Mid-point section depth, salinity measurement	[m]
dz_S	[Nr,61]	Section thickness, salinity measurement	[m]
cl_S	[Nr]	Length of salinity core	[m]
tsl_S	[Nr]	Total section length, salinity core	[m]
Nd_S	[Nr]	Number of core sections with valid salinity record	
Nb_S	[Nr]	Number of S-core sections in log-sheet (including empty cells)	
S_mean	[Nr]	Vertically-averaged ice salinity (weighted by section length)	[g/kg]
S_max	[Nr]	Maximum salinity in the core	[g/kg]
S_min	[Nr]	Minimum salinity in the core	[g/kg]

Name	Size	Definition	Units
S_std	[Nr]	Standard deviation of salinity in the core	[g/kg]
T_mean	[Nr]	Vertically-averaged ice temperature	[°C]
T_max	[Nr]	Maximum temperature in the core	[°C]
T_min	[Nr]	Minimum temperature in the core	[°C]
T_std	[Nr]	Standard deviation of temperature in the core	[°C]
year	[Nr]	Sampling year	[year]
mon	[Nr]	Sampling month	[mon]
doy	[Nr]	Sampling day-of-year	[doy]
i_keep_S	[Nr]	Flag signalling a unique (1) or duplicate (0) S-core	[0/1]
i_keep_T	[Nr]	Flag signalling a unique (1) or duplicate (0) T-core	[0/1]
reff	[Nr]	Reference publication	string
region	[Nr]	Region explored during cruise	string

Table S2. Field campaigns incorporated in the compilation (Northern Hemisphere). Age class is either first-year (FY) or multi-year (MY) ice; drift class is either pack (P) or fast (F) ice. N_S is the number of salinity cores, whereas N_T is the number of temperature cores.

Cruise name	Region	Years	Months	Age Class	Drift Class	Core length (m)	N_S	N_T	Reference
NP-23 77	Central Arctic	1977-1978	2-10	MY	P	2.29 ± 0.30	0	8	Melnikov (1997)
ARKTIS-XI/1 95	Laptev / Central Arctic	1995-1995	7-9	MY	P	1.57 ± 0.62	23	0	Rachor (1995)
ARKTIS-XIII/1 97	Barents / Fram Strait	1997-1997	5-6	FY/MY	P	2.33 ± 1.26	13	13	Spindler et al. (1997)
ARKTIS-XIII/2 97	Central Arctic	1997-1997	6-7	MY	P	2.23 ± 0.54	12	12	Stein and Fahl (1997)
SHEBA	Beaufort	1998-1998	4-8	FY/MY	P	1.98 ± 0.71	20	6	Perovich et al. (1999)
ARKTIS-XV/3 99	Central Arctic / Fram Strait	1999-1999	9-10	FY/MY	P	1.62 ± 0.79	10	11	Schauer (2000)
Barrow 99-01	Beaufort	1999-2001	2-12	FY	F	0.90 ± 0.45	59	49	Vancoppenolle et al. (2007)
ARKTIS-XVI/2 00	Fram Strait	2000-2000	8-8	MY	P	2.51 ± 0.58	6	5	Krause and Schauer (2001)
CASES 04	Canadian Arctic (Amundsen Gulf)	2003-2004	1-12	FY	F	1.52 ± 0.36	23	21	Miller et al. (2011), Rysgaard et al. (2007)
Daneborg 05	Greenland (Daneborg)	2005-2005	3-3	FY	F	0.96 ± 0.22	5	5	Rysgaard et al. (2007)
B76	Lincoln	2006-2006	4-4	FY/MY	P	1.84 ± 0.99	10	10	S. Rysgaard (unpub)
ARKTIS-XXII/2 07	Central Arctic	2007-2007	8-9	FY/MY	P	1.63 ± 0.45	11	11	Schauer (2008)
ATOS 07	Central Arctic	2007-2007	7-7	MY	P	1.00 ± 0.00	8	0	Tovar-Sanchez et al. (2010)
TARA 07	Central Arctic	2007-2007	5-9	FY/MY	P	1.77 ± 0.23	22	0	J. Haapala, M. Nicolaus (unpub)
CFL 07-08	Canadian Arctic (Amundsen Gulf)	2007-2008	1-12	FY	F/P	0.98 ± 0.46	61	60	Carnat et al. (2013)
JOIS-IPY-C30	Beaufort / Central Arctic	2008-2009	8-12	FY/MY	P	1.72 ± 1.47	8	6	Brown et al. (2014)
CHINARE	Central Arctic	2008-2018	7-9	FY/MY	P	1.30 ± 0.36	41	33	Wang et al. (2020)
BASICS-SIZONET	Beaufort	2009-2009	1-6	FY	F	1.15 ± 0.24	10	10	Zhou et al. (2010)
IPY-ArcticNet	Beaufort / Central Arctic	2009-2009	9-9	MY	P	2.62 ± 1.59	3	0	Brown et al. (2014)
Resolute 10	Canadian Arctic (Resolute)	2010-2010	5-6	FY	F	1.41 ± 0.08	11	11	Brown et al. (2015)
ARKTIS-XXVI/3 11	Central Arctic	2011-2011	8-9	FY/MY	P	1.87 ± 0.45	11	11	Schauer (2012)
CAS 2011	Canadian Arctic (Qikiqtaaluk)	2011-2011	3-4	FY	F	1.72 ± 0.12	4	4	K. Brown (unpub)
JCR 2011	Fram Strait	2011-2011	6-6	FY	P	0.89 ± 0.07	3	3	S. Rysgaard (unpub)
ARKTIS-XXVII/3 12	Central Arctic	2012-2012	8-9	FY/MY	P	1.17 ± 0.38	10	10	Boetius (2013)
Resolute 12	Canadian Arctic (Resolute)	2012-2012	6-6	FY	F	1.15 ± 0.11	6	6	Geilfus et al. (2015)
Daneborg 14	Greenland (Daneborg)	2014-2014	5-6	FY	F	1.41 ± 0.04	6	6	Geilfus et al. (2023)
SIRAS 14	Okhotsk	2014-2018	2-2	FY	P	0.65 ± 0.36	9	9	D. Nomura (unpub)
N-ICE	Central Arctic	2015-2015	1-6	FY/MY	P	1.15 ± 0.26	23	0	Assmy et al. (2017)
Station Nord 15	Greenland (Station Nord)	2015-2015	5-5	FY	F	1.30 ± 0.21	13	13	Geilfus et al. (2021)
OPTIMISM 15-18	Svalbard	2015-2018	4-4	FY	F	0.52 ± 0.13	18	21	Lebrun et al. (2023)
ICE-CAMPS (2016)	Canadian Arctic (Cambridge Bay)	2016-2016	5-5	FY	F	1.75 ± 0.07	6	6	L. Dalman (unpub)
BaySys	Hudson Bay	2017-2017	2-4	FY	F	1.01 ± 0.32	31	8	L. Dalman (unpub)
Cambridge Bay 18	Canadian Arctic (Cambridge Bay)	2018-2018	4-4	FY	F	1.55 ± 0.05	2	1	L. Dalman (unpub)
Saroma 18-19	Hokkaido (Saroma)	2018-2019	2-3	FY	F	0.41 ± 0.04	6	6	D. Nomura (unpub)
CAATEX 19	Central Arctic	2019-2019	8-9	MY	P	1.24 ± 0.35	12	9	Raffel et al. (2023)
CBAY 19	Canadian Arctic (Cambridge Bay)	2019-2019	5-5	FY	F	1.74 ± 0.11	3	3	Else et al. (2022)
MOSAIC	Central Arctic	2019-2020	1-12	FY/MY	P	1.51 ± 0.63	97	101	Oggier et al. (2024, 2025), Salganik et al. (2024, 2025), Nomura (unpub)
Coral Harbour 21	Hudson Bay	2021-2021	5-6	FY	F	1.51 ± 0.10	23	28	K. Campbell (unpub)

Table S3. Field campaigns incorporated in the compilation (Southern Hemisphere).

Cruise name	Region	Years	Months	Age Class	Drift Class	Core length (m)	N _S	N _T	Reference
WEPOLEX	Weddell (Maud Rise)	1981-1981	10-11	FY	P	0.66 ± 0.18	14	0	Clarke and Ackley (1984)
ANTARKTIS V-2 (WWSP86)	East Weddell	1986-1986	7-9	FY/MY	P	0.82 ± 0.83	31	0	Schnack-Schiel (1987), Dieckmann et al. (1991)
ANTARKTIS V-3 (WWSP86)	East Weddell	1986-1986	10-12	FY/MY	P	0.82 ± 0.50	25	0	Schnack-Schiel (1987), Dieckmann et al. (1991)
AMERIEZ 88	Weddell / Scotia	1988-1988	6-6	FY	P	0.46 ± 0.30	14	0	Garrison et al. (1993)
ANTARKTIS VII-2 (EPOS 1)	West Weddell	1988-1988	10-11	FY/MY	P	1.57 ± 0.92	21	0	Hempel (1989)
ANTARKTIS VIII-2	Weddell	1989-1989	9-10	FY/MY	P	1.36 ± 0.57	7	0	Augstein et al. (1991)
ANTARKTIS IX-3	East Weddell	1991-1991	1-2	FY/MY	P	1.71 ± 0.40	20	0	Bathmann et al. (1992)
AAD-91-94	East Antarctica	1991-1994	3-11	FY/MY	P	0.76 ± 0.58	93	0	Worby and Massom (1995)
ANTARKTIS X-3	East Weddell	1992-1992	4-5	FY/MY	P	0.60 ± 0.40	18	0	Spindler et al. (1993)
ANTARKTIS XI-3	Amundsen / Bellingshausen	1994-1994	2-3	FY/MY	P	2.03 ± 1.11	16	0	Miller and Grobe (1996)
ANTARKTIS XIV-3	Weddell	1997-1997	1-3	FY/MY	P	0.40 ± 0.46	37	0	Miller (1996), Haas (1998), Kennedy et al. (2002)
AURORA1997-V2	Indian / Pacific	1997-1997	10-10	FY/MY	P	0.80 ± 0.56	17	0	Trevena et al. (2000)
PIPEX-PIED	Ross (Terra Nova)	1997-1999	11-11	FY/MY	P	2.22 ± 0.50	25	0	Lazzara et al. (2007)
AURORA98-V4	Pacific	1998-1998	11-11	FY/MY	P	1.45 ± 0.67	5	0	Trevena and Jones (2006)
ROAVERRS 98	Ross	1998-1998	11-12	FY/MY	P	0.57 ± 0.31	82	0	Arrigo et al. (2003)
PNRA XVI 00-01	Ross (Terra Nova)	2000-2001	1-12	FY/MY	P	2.50 ± 0.00	10	0	Grotti et al. (2005)
ANTARKTIS XVIII-5b	Amundsen / Bellingshausen	2001-2001	4-4	FY	P	0.62 ± 0.13	3	3	Meiners et al. (2004)
AURORA03-V1	Pacific	2003-2003	9-10	FY	P	0.65 ± 0.24	20	20	Lannuzel et al. (2007)
ScottBase 03	Ross (McMurdo)	2003-2003	1-1	FY/MY	F	2.54 ± 0.74	6	1	de Jong et al. (2013)
ANTARKTIS XXII-2 - ISPOL	Weddell	2004-2004	11-12	FY/MY	P	1.03 ± 0.44	70	42	Lannuzel et al. (2008), Tison et al. (2008)
PNRA XX 04-05	Ross	2004-2004	11-12	FY/MY	F	1.64 ± 0.49	35	0	Grotti et al. (2005)
SIMBA 07	Amundsen / Bellingshausen	2004-2007	10-10	FY	P	0.84 ± 0.20	30	20	Lewis et al. (2011), Fritsen et al. (2011), de Jong et al. (2015)
ANTARKTIS XXIII-7 (WWOS 2006)	Weddell	2006-2006	9-10	FY/MY	P	1.25 ± 0.28	11	0	Meiners et al. (2009)
SIPEX	Pacific	2007-2007	9-10	FY	P	0.78 ± 0.36	36	35	Meiners et al. (2011), van der Merwe et al. (2009), van der Merwe et al. (2011)
OSO 08-09	Amundsen / Ross	2008-2009	1-12	FY	P	1.47 ± 0.64	18	18	Fransson et al. (2011)
Casey 09	Pacific (Casey)	2009-2009	11-12	FY	F	1.20 ± 0.01	16	16	van der Merwe et al. (2011)
ICELIPIDS	Adelie Land	2011-2011	4-11	FY	F	1.17 ± 0.39	10	0	Fripiat et al. (2017)
YROSIAE 11-12	Ross (McMurdo)	2011-2012	9-12	FY	F	1.65 ± 0.08	23	23	Carnat et al. (2014)
SIPEX-2	Pacific	2012-2012	9-10	FY/MY	P	1.10 ± 0.43	18	13	Meiners et al. (2016), Lannuzel et al. (2016)
AWECS-12	Weddell	2013-2013	6-7	FY	P	0.56 ± 0.42	16	16	Tison et al. (2017)
Rothera RS 13-15	Bellingshausen	2013-2015	7-12	FY	F	0.69 ± 0.18	13	13	Meiners et al. (2018), van Leeuwe and Stefels (unpub.)
Filchner 14	Weddell	2014-2014	1-1	FY	F	1.32 ± 0.06	2	1	Meiners et al. (2018)
AURORA17-V2	Pacific	2016-2017	1-12	FY/MY	P	1.62 ± 0.40	9	9	Duprat et al. (2020)
JARE 16-19	Indian (Syowa)	2016-2019	1-2	FY/MY	F	1.86 ± 0.67	6	0	D. Nomura (unpub)
PIPERS 17	Ross	2017-2017	4-6	FY	P	0.38 ± 0.21	22	22	Tison et al. (2020)
DMLEC	King Hakon	2019-2019	3-3	FY	P	0.20 ± 0.00	1	0	S. Moreau (unpub)
PS118	Weddell	2019-2019	2-3	FY	P	1.59 ± 0.76	35	0	I. Peeken (unpub)

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